

JURISPRUDENCE

THE PRIORITY OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION IN THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE SOCIETY

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Abstract

In this article the relations of science, education and society are presented and the role of science and education is highlighted in the development of society.

Keywords: society, education, science, world community, development, priority, family, cooperate.

The society is the life style of the people who live and work together in communications. The formation of the society begins with the family, which is considered to be the smallest part of the society. The families form the community of people (we call it Mahalla'). In their part, they together form districts, cities and regions. The countries are formed from the cities and regions. If we look to this position from the global point of view our country. Uzbekistan is also one of the members of the world society. So, the beginning of this great community is a family. On the basis of this point of view, we would like to highlight the role of a family in the formation, strengthening and stability of the society. Each member of the family has its place in the family. So, Uzbekistan has also its own place in the world community.

There are different stages in the development of the society and each of these stages are differentiated from one another taking into account social, economic, political and cultural peculiarities. The great changes in the development of the society are usually carried out by reforms. The reforms positively influence on the development of the society by changing its quality and also determines the possible changes in the future.

The socio-political processes, which go on in the society, will influence on the life style of the people who are the members of this society. In other words, the people are also involved into this process. In such cases, one of the political trends, i.e., one of the political parties, can take the management into their hands and the theory of socio-political processes, define the essence of such process.

After the Independence of Uzbekistan, there have been worked out five principles of reforming the society in Uzbekistan. These principles are the following:

- the priority of economy than the politics;
- the state is the leading reformer;
- the priority of laws in all spheres of the society;
- the demographic state of the population;
- the fulfillment of the rules of market economy.

These reforms projected the new stage of the development of our country. The main points of this project include peace, stability, open-heartedness and friendly relations among the citizens and nations who live in Uzbekistan. The role and place of the science and education should be highlighted in the development of every society. In the formation of a new democratic society the purposeful use of the achievement of

science and new technologies, the upbringing of young generation under the spiritual, national dignity are the main factors of creating new independent development of our country. It should be stressed that the modern science and new technologies are the important force or the motor of the development of the society.

At present when we discuss the achievements of science and technologies, it is also important to stress out their contribution into the development of the society, because these achievements of the science and new technologies are being implemented in all spheres of the society. It is obvious that science is the main tool in defining the relations and interdependence between natural laws and human nature and thought. The development of the society at the present stage can be proved by the development of the science. The spheres of the science are various and such branches of the science as chemistry, physics, mathematics, biology, genetics, embryology, linguistics and other sciences can be used in all spheres of human activity. A science is always in action, it doesn't stop at a place but it always develops and there exist new branches of the science. As the development of the world is endless, so is the science. It always goes further and discovers the new secrets of nature and possibilities of human being. This process is also endless.

In the development of science we should focus our attention on two ways of its development: theoretical and practical. They are interdependent and closely relate to each other by presenting proofs in their arguments. Every novelty discovered from the theoretical point of view is usually implemented into practice. Then there appeared new and new ideas about this novelty. Every science has its own aim, tasks, principles, methods, and means of investigation. Every scientific idea can be proved when it gives results after being implemented into practice. The other main factor besides science in human activity is education. It is significant in creating a person's character, outlook, relations to other people. A well educated person takes an active part in all spheres of the society and contributes to the development of the society. The level of education can also be seen in the person's behavior, in communication with others and making correct decision in solving different social problems. It should be stressed that the psychological factors play an important role in the formation of spiritual character of a person. The main task of education can be seen in creating consions relation

to the formation of individual features of a person's modesty. When a person learns events and things around he/she should have a definite aim because everything seems attractive for a young individual. But a middle aged person becomes more restrained and cautions in making decisions. This shows that there should be different approach in educating and creating personal individual and also social features at different age stages of a person. In educating young generation the following features are essential: culturedness, modesty, knowledge, honesty, patriotism and others. These features are the criteries of spiritual maturity of a person.

The education, science, and society are not static they always in development harmonious with the time. The triangle, which is formed by education, science, and society are the main factors in the development of the world. All countries, as a part of global community can contribute in the development of the world by communicating in all spheres of life and the main tool of communication is the language. At present English has become the language of communication throughout the world. That is why much attention is being paid to learning and teaching English in our country too. This can be seen in a number of state documents relating to teaching foreign languages in Uzbekistan. As an example it should be mentioned a state document "The measures on developing the quality of teaching foreign languages at the Educational institutions" adopted in Uzbekistan.

At present learning English is a need for all specialists of national economy, because it is not only the language of communication but also the tool of implementing foreign technologies in their practical activities. The social development of the society depends much on the relations of science and education. The scientific sight of the world forms the basis of modern education and the human factor is in the center of education. In other words, the unity of science, education and society is the main force of social development.

In this case, the human factor plays a significant role in developing society. That is why training a qualified specialists, who can answer modern requirements and improving their scientific-innovative activity is the task put for all types of educational institutions, especially for high education: institutes and universities.

Three types of educational institutions are responsible for training specialists for national economy. They are colleges, technical schools, and high schools (institutes and universities). This means that much depends on the pedagogical and professional activities of the teachers who work in these educational institutions in training well-qualified modern specialists, because the professional knowledge, professional proficiency of the teachers are significant factors in training specialists. Besides these teaching programs, manuals and textbooks should be compiled according to modern requirements.

In conclusion, we would like to stress once more that the unity of science and education is motor for developing society. And the need for highly qualified specialists who are able to cooperate with foreign partners can be fulfilled by teaching them foreign languages, especially the English language, because it is the key for getting information from the foreign sources and establishing a good cooperation with their foreign colleagues in the field of their profession.

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